

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FACTORS THAT HINDER SOCIAL ADAPTATION IN STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

This scientific work provides an in-depth analysis of psychological and pedagogical factors affecting the social adaptation process of students with disabilities. The study highlights the impact of the psycho-emotional state of students, family environment, conditions in educational institutions, professional training of teachers, communicative relations in the team, and the quality of inclusive education on adaptation. It also suggests pedagogical approaches, types of psychological support, and innovative methods necessary for successful social adaptation. The results of the study provide practical recommendations for educators, psychologists, and educational organizers working with children with disabilities.

In modern society, the comprehensive development of students with disabilities, their full involvement in the educational process and their formation as active participants in the life of society are one of the most important social tasks. The social adaptation of such students is a complex process, which depends on their individual psychological characteristics, level of intellectual and emotional development, family circumstances, quality of pedagogical support and the level of inclusiveness of the educational environment. Current research shows that students with disabilities or developmental disabilities often face psychological barriers such as communicative limitations, low self-esteem, feeling isolated from the community, and lack of social activity. At the same time, some shortcomings in the pedagogical process - low special training of teachers, lack of a differentiated approach, unadapted learning environment, and the formation of inappropriate relationships between students - have a negative impact on their adaptation. Therefore, both scientific analysis and practical proposals covering the factors affecting the social adaptation of students with disabilities are very important today. This topic is aimed at revealing the mechanisms by which a student can find his place in society, form a positive self-esteem, adapt to independent life and fully demonstrate his capabilities. The roots of the phenomena should be sought in the distant history of our people. The education of students with disabilities can be included in the list of responsible tasks such as helping them adapt to social life by teaching them to read and write, effectively implementing these tasks, and providing practical assistance to special workers and parents of students with disabilities. The main problems of students with disabilities cannot be solved by educating them away from the environment in

which they live, away from their families. Unless society assumes responsibility for its members, it must provide them with opportunities and facilities to exercise their limited rights and opportunities.

Solving the problem of equality in the education of students with special needs is one of the urgent problems of today. However, even today, many students are excluded from education for various reasons. By involving them in inclusive education, we need to implement organizational, scientific and methodological measures, as well as develop measures for the training and improvement of their qualifications. There are two main factors in attracting students with special needs to general education institutions:

Firstly, students with special needs can also interact with healthy students. If inclusive education is organized in a purposeful way, students with special needs will be socially protected, and healthy students will feel the greatness of social justice and recognition of equality, and will be more kind and attentive to students with disabilities.

Secondly, students with disabilities also have the right to study and be educated alongside their able-bodied peers.

In order to successfully implement such work, it is necessary to reflect it in the laws of each country. In providing education to students with special educational needs, it is required and considered a mandatory condition that parents, neighborhoods, educators, and specialists work together.

Students with disabilities can also work, receive education, learn a profession and develop at the level of their abilities together with healthy peers. If inclusive education is organized in a purposeful manner, students in need of special assistance will be socially protected, feel that they have equal rights in social life, can receive education and acquire skills along with their peers.

Although the existing defects of students in integrated-special, closed institutions established for students with disabilities are corrected to a much higher degree, their adaptation to society as a result of their inclusion in a narrow circle of the school community is hampered. Special schools have great shortcomings in these aspects. In addition, it is not democratic to keep students with special needs completely separated from the general public. Because students with special needs also have all the rights. We can also see this at the conference held in Jomtien (Thailand) in 1990. This conference aimed to formulate the goal of "Education for All", and it was attended by representatives of 155 countries and experts from more than 150 non-governmental organizations. The analysis shows that

It is shown that approximately 10-15% of students need special education, which is supported by facts.

In order to support and analyze the implementation of the slogan "Education for All" on the basis of the conference held in Jomtien (Thailand), in 1994, the Salamanca-Spain World Conference was held in cooperation with UNESCO and the Spanish government. The goal and task of the participants of this conference were to create conditions for students with special needs to receive education in general education institutions around the world, to discuss the need for school reforms to fulfill the task of teaching in schools.

The need to involve students with special needs in general education institutions is reflected in the fact that the final working documents were studied based on integrated

education programs in Africa and Southeast Asia. As a result, in each country's Ministries of Education, special schools were established

Inclusive working methods are being adopted as an alternative to the activities of special departments. Placing students in boarding schools far from their families and homes prevents their right to participate in the life of their homes and families. A child who is far from their homes, families, and parental love grows up to be very sensitive. Because the family is the main center of upbringing. In every society, misconceptions and attitudes towards people with disabilities were very high. The main reason for this was the lack of information about them and the fact that they were educated and raised in special institutions from a young age. Organizing various practical activities to eliminate and reduce such attitudes is a rather difficult task. However, experience shows that students, compared to adults, understand differences and similarities faster. If students with special needs were educated together with students with normal development, this would ensure that all students understand that they are children like them and do not discriminate against those with disabilities.

When diagnosing the formation of positive attitudes towards social life of students with disabilities, the need to solve it on the basis of the integration of knowledge is determined by the study of the formation of positive attitudes towards social life of students.

In terms of structure, the pedagogical model should include components that allow it to be changed and corrected, affect the effectiveness of activities and are easily diagnosed. The pedagogical model with a two-part structure is the most common model.

A model is a template that provides for the successful resolution of problem situations arising in various areas, describes certain qualities and reflects its independent acquisition of knowledge and self-development.

When creating this model, a set of personal qualities is regulated, which are suitable for a certain type of activity. One of the types of the specialist model is a qualification profile. Its content reflects the following situations:

types of activities, tasks and responsibilities, personal qualities, knowledge and skills that are characteristic of each student with special needs in order to form a positive attitude to social life. Such models are of great importance in their selection and placement, testing, as well as in their preparation and development of programs.

The principle of modeling the formation of positive attitudes to social life of students with special educational needs in the educational process. Modeling is a scientific method that allows you to create various models of an object of knowledge and use them in scientific creativity. Modeling is to work or create a model of something.

Modeling is necessary to organize education on a scientific basis in order to form positive attitudes towards social life of students with special educational needs, to organize education on a scientific basis, to implement the educational process (independent education, upbringing, self-education) and to take into account modern requirements, students' needs, students' worldview and initial concepts, tasks for independent study, students' capabilities, the purpose, subject and importance of the subject and topics being taught, and to select appropriate educational methods, determine the tasks to be implemented and the stages of their implementation. In order to prove the content and goals through modeling, it is necessary to first master easy knowledge, and to select teaching methods based on the

requirements of the curriculum and curriculum. In the educational process, a wide range of work activities are carried out on the basis of the following conditions:

- a) orientation of knowledge and skills;
- b) integrated training
- c) the process of transfer training.

Despite the diversity of approaches to modeling the personality and activities of students with special educational needs, scientific research has not studied the problem of creating a model of personal development, as well as the process of professional training in the system of preparation for social life. British scientist M. Rosenberg developed nine areas and the following requirements for them:

- > Knowledge of the needs and requirements of students;
- > Ability to assess the effectiveness of activities;
- > Possession of competence;
- > Possession of communicative competence;
- > Possession of abilities;
- > Achieving continuous improvement of their social life;
- > Achieving cultural improvement of their personality.

A model for the formation of positive attitudes of students with disabilities to social life should be created from the most general knowledge to specific skills. The most common is the ability to think and act, which is associated with the ability to study facts and phenomena for theoretical analysis. The basis of general and specific skills is a process of transition that continues at the empirical and theoretical levels.

The form of manifestation of theoretical preparation is theoretical activity, which is manifested in the generalized ability of pedagogical thinking, which presupposes the possession of analytical, prognostic, projective, reflexive skills.

Conclusion , the model for the formation of positive attitudes of students with special educational needs to social life and the pedagogical features based on the principle of modular preparation of the educational process should include.

Practical application of modeling is based on the development of an educational model for the formation of positive attitudes of students with limited cognitive abilities to social life, which is based on the isolation of all structural elements of didactic activity, the determination of the significance of these structural elements for the system of inclusive education and the establishment of interrelationships between them: identification of typical tasks that must be solved to form positive attitudes of students with special educational needs to social life, ensuring the training of highly qualified workers in the sectors; development of educational and production goals and objectives on their basis, comprehensively covering the activities of students with special educational needs; determination of the place of these tasks in the educational structure; selection of optimal forms and methods of teaching when considering each task.

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